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How Likely Special UN Adviser Jeffrey Sachs Has Been Bribed by China

(Picture source: UN-Page)

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1 [Who is Jeffrey Sachs](#)

He is Special Advisor to United Nations Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon on the Sustainable Development Goals, and previously advised both UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon and UN Secretary-General Kofi Annan on the Millennium Development Goals. currently Director of both the Center for Sustainable Development, and the UN Sustainable Development Solutions Network under the auspices of UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon. co-founder and Chief Strategist of Millennium Promise Alliance, and is director of the Millennium Villages Project. Sachs is also one of the Secretary-General’s SDG Advocates, and a Commissioner of the ITU/UNESCO Broadband Commission for Development.

Jeffrey D. Sachs, a native of Detroit, Michigan, received B.A., M.A., and Ph.D. degrees at Harvard and spent over twenty years as a professor at Harvard University. Thereafter, Sachs was appointed University Professor at Columbia University in 2016, and serves as Quetelet Professor of Sustainable Development, and Professor of Health Policy and Management at Columbia University. A Fellow of the International Institute of Applied Systems Analysis in Laxenburg, Austria.

2 [What activities Jeffrey Sachs has been engaged in China](#)

2.1 [Brookings-Tsinghua Center for Public Policy: Lecturer](#)

On 8 March 2007 Jeffrey D. Sachs gave a lecture on The State of the World Economy and Ecology in Tsinghua University, Beijing, China.

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清华-布鲁金斯公共政策研究中心
BROOKINGS-TSINGHUA CENTER FOR PUBLIC POLICY

BRIEFINGS

SN : BR20070308CH VOLUME 6

The State of the World Economy and Ecology

【Preface】 Since the commencement of economic reform and opening-up, China has experienced high growth for thirty years, and the world is showing an economic convergence trend. Can China sustain the momentum of rapid growth in coming decades? What problem will challenge the development of China and the world in the long-term? To answer these questions, Brookings-Tsinghua Center for Public Policy invited Professor Jeffrey Sachs to give a lecture on world economy and ecology. He is the Director of Earth Institute at Columbia University, father of "shock therapy" in Soviet Russia, and was cited by Time Magazine as "most important economist in the world", He claimed that environment problems

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TOPIC: The State of the World Economy and Ecology

ORGANIZER: Brookings-Tsinghua Center for Public Policy

TIME & PLACE: March 8, 2007; Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

MODERATOR:

Xiao Geng, Director, Brookings-Tsinghua Center for Public Policy

LECTURER:

Jeffrey D. Sachs, Director, Earth Institute at Columbia University

DISCUSSANTS:

Yi Gang, Assistant Governor, People's Bank of China

Fan Gang, Director, National Economic Research Institute

Hu Angang, Director, Center for China Study at Tsinghua University

中国北京 清华大学 公共管理学院 100084
电话: +86-10-6279-7363 传真: +86-10-6279-7659 电邮: brookings@tsinghua.edu.cn
<http://www.brookings.edu/brookings-tsinghua.aspx>

(Picture source: brookings)

2.2 China Development Research Foundation: Senior Advisor of Children Development Center

1. What is China Development Research Foundation(CDRF)?

According to the Constitution of CDRF, its aim is to research policies, promote scientific policy decision, promote development of China while it observed core values of socialism. It insisted comprehensive leadership of Chinese Communist Party and established cell units of CCP. Its incorporation fund,40 million RMB, came from donations of Beijing Commodities Exchange, Hang Lung Group and Zhuhai Brilliance Holdings Ltd.

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政策研究

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- 组织结构

中国发展研究基金会高级顾问

Evan Due
杜伊文

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- 信息公开
- 我们的团队
- 国际研究人员
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中国发展研究基金会高级顾问

Evan Due
杜伊文

儿童发展中心高级顾问

Jeffrey D. Sachs
杰弗里·萨克斯

Amartya Sen
阿马蒂亚·森

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中国发展研究基金会章程

第一章 总则

第一条 本基金会的名称是中国发展研究基金会，英文译名为：China Development Research Foundation，缩写为：CDRF。

第二条 本基金会属于具有公开募捐资格的基金会。

本基金会按照《中华人民共和国慈善法》、《慈善组织公开募捐管理办法》等相关规定，开展公开募捐。

第三条 本基金会的宗旨是支持政策研究，促进科学决策，服务中国发展。

本基金会遵守宪法、法律、法规和国家政策，践行社会主义核心价值观，弘扬爱国主义精神，遵守社会道德风尚，自觉加强诚信自律建设。

第四条 本基金会坚持中国共产党的全面领导，根据中国共产党章程的规定，设立中国共产党的组织，开展党的活动，为党的活动提供必要条件。

第五条 本基金会的原始基金数额为人民币4000万元，来源于北京商品交易所、恒隆集团有限公司、珠海华晨控股有限责任公司的捐赠。

第六条 本基金会的登记管理机关是民政部，业务主管单位是国务院发展研究中心。

第七条 本基金会住所设在北京市。

第二章 业务范围

第八条 本基金会公益活动的业务范围是：

- (一) 支持政策咨询和学术研究活动；
- (二) 开展国际交流与合作；
- (三) 组织人员培训；
- (四) 奖励在政策咨询和学术研究方面作出突出贡献的人员；
- (五) 资助符合基金会宗旨的其他社会公益活动。

业务范围内属于法律法规规章规定须经批准的事项，依法经批准后开展。

(Picture source:CDRF)

Development Research Center of the State Council of the People's Republic of China is in charge of its business: (1) Support policy consultation and academic research activities;(2) Carrying out international exchanges and cooperation;(3) Organizing personnel training;(4) Reward personnel who have made outstanding contributions in policy consultation and academic research;(5) Funding other social welfare activities in line with the purpose of the foundation.

Its directors are mainly CCP officials. Numeration committee members are mainly CCP officials.

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中国发展研究基金会第四届理事会理事

(按姓氏笔画)

- | | |
|-----|--|
| 王佩亨 | 国务院发展研究中心机关党委原副书记 |
| 方 晋 | 中国发展研究基金会秘书长 |
| 卢 迈 | 中国发展研究基金会副理事长 |
| 朱云来 | 金融专业人士 |
| 任兴洲 | 国务院发展研究中心市场经济研究所原所长 |
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中国发展研究基金会副理事长 |
| 孙 杰 | 中国证券投资基金业协会原会长 |
| 孙祁祥 | 北京大学经济学院教授 |
| 吕 薇 | 全国人大常委会委员、国务院发展研究中心创新发展研究部
原部长 |

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- 李 伟 全国政协人口资源环境委员会主任、国务院发展研究中心原
主任、中国发展研究基金会理事长
- 沈南鹏 红杉资本全球执行合伙人、红杉资本中国基金创始及执行合
伙人
- 陈小洪 国务院发展研究中心企业研究所原所长
- 陈东琪 国家发改委宏观经济研究院原副院长
- 赵令欢 弘毅投资董事长、总裁
- 赵晋平 国务院发展研究中心对外经济研究部原部长
- 林家彬 国务院发展研究中心研究员
- 张小济 国务院发展研究中心对外经济研究部原部长
- 张文中 物美集团创始人、多点 **Dmall** 董事长
- 张志洲 敦和资产管理公司首席执行官
- 张承惠 国务院发展研究中心金融研究所原所长
- 钱颖一 清华大学经济管理学院教授
- 薛 澜 清华大学苏世民书院院长

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中国发展研究基金会第四届理事会资产与薪酬委员会名单

(7人)

主任委员 刘世锦

委员（按姓氏笔画排序） 吕薇、赵晋平、王佩亨、朱云来、赵令欢、张志洲

画排序)

(Picture source:CDRF)

2. Who else have been on the payroll?

Evan Due, Senior Fellow at the Institute of Asian Research, University of British Columbia and Senior Advisor to the China Development Research Foundation in Beijing China, He has held positions in the Government of Canada with the Canadian International Development Agency (now Global Affairs Canada) and the International Development Research Centre, and consultancy positions with the United Nations, the Norwegian Agency for International Cooperation, and the Government of Sri Lanka.

Evan Due

Evan Due

Evan Due is a policy research and management consultant. He is a senior advisor to the China Development Research Foundation in Beijing China, and a senior fellow at the Institute of Asian Research, University of British Columbia, Canada. He has more than 25 years experience in international relations and development, policy analysis, and program management. He has held positions in the Government of Canada with the Canadian International Development Agency (now Global Affairs Canada) and the International Development Research Centre, and consultancy positions with the United Nations, the Norwegian Agency for International Cooperation, and the Government of Sri Lanka. He represented Canada at OECD Development Assistance Committee, and in various multilateral forums. His professional interests are in public policy, political economy, international trade and economic governance. He obtained his doctorate from the University of Sussex, U.K.

Return

Amartya Sen, Thomas W. Lamont University Professor, and Professor of Economics and Philosophy, at Harvard University. Senior Fellow at the Harvard Society of Fellows. Earlier on Professor of Economics at Jadavpur University Calcutta, the Delhi School of

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Economics, and the London School of Economics, and Drummond Professor of Political Economy at Oxford University. Amartya Sen has served as President of the Econometric Society, the American Economic Association, the Indian Economic Association, and the International Economic Association.

Amartya Sen

Amartya Sen

Amartya Sen is Thomas W. Lamont University Professor, and Professor of Economics and Philosophy, at Harvard University and was until 2004 the Master of Trinity College, Cambridge. He is also Senior Fellow at the Harvard Society of Fellows. Earlier on he was Professor of Economics at Jadavpur University Calcutta, the Delhi School of Economics, and the London School of Economics, and Drummond Professor of Political Economy at Oxford University.

Amartya Sen has served as President of the Econometric Society, the American Economic Association, the Indian Economic Association, and the International Economic Association. His research has ranged over social choice theory, economic theory, ethics and political philosophy, welfare economics, theory of measurement, decision theory, development economics, public health, and gender studies. Amartya Sen's books have been translated into more than thirty languages, and include Choice of Techniques (1960), Growth Economics (1970), Collective Choice and Social

(Picture source:CDRF)

3. What happened?

In Mar 2017 Jeffrey Sachs is a foreign guest to China Development Forum directed by Development Research Center of PRC State Council and undertaken by China Development Research Center. Previously he attended the forum held in 2015.

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中国发展高层论坛 2017
CHINA DEVELOPMENT FORUM

与世界对话·谋共同发展
Engaging with the world for the common prosperity

时间: 2017年3月18 - 20日
地点: 北京·钓鱼台国宾馆

主办: 国务院发展研究中心
承办: 中国发展研究基金会

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杰弗里·萨克斯
Jeffrey Sachs

美国哥伦比亚大学教授、地球研究所所长 **学者**

杰弗里·萨克斯是世界著名的经济学教授，可持续发展的领路人，联合国高级顾问，畅销书作家，专栏作家。他的专栏文章每月在超过100个国家的报纸上发表。

2002年到2016年期间，萨克斯教授任职哥伦比亚大学地球研究所所长、可持续发展研究克托莱教授、医疗政策及管理学教授。他是联合国秘书长潘基文关于千年发展目标的特殊顾问，在此之前他也为前秘书长科菲·安南担任同一职务。他是奥地利拉克森堡全球应用系统分析研究所的荣誉研究员。萨克斯不仅主管可持续发展中心，在联合国秘书长潘基文的支持下，他也是联合国可持续发展解决方案网络的主任。

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参会嘉宾

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世界经济大趋势

(Picture source: cdf)

On 19 October 2018 Jeffrey D. Sachs, Sonia Sachs Ehrlich (director of Center for Sustainable Development Ministry of Health of the Earth Institute at Columbia University), Guido Schmidt-Traub (director of the United Nations sustainable development solutions

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network) and the team members visited China Development Research Foundation.

2018年10月19日下午，哥伦比亚大学可持续发展研究中心主任杰弗里·萨克斯（Jeffrey D. Sachs）、哥伦比亚大学地球研究所可持续发展中心卫生部主任索尼娅·埃里克·萨克斯（Sonia Ehrlich Sachs）、联合国可持续发展解决方案网络（SDSN）主任吉多·施密特·特劳布（Guido Schmidt-Traub）一行到访中国发展研究基金会。杰弗里·萨克斯（Jeffrey D. Sachs）教授一行与基金会卢迈副理事长会见后，参观了基金会，随后参加基金会“毕节市建设贯彻新发展理念示范区研究”课题组专家咨询会，与基金会领导、毕节市领导共同探讨毕节市新发展理念示范区的发展规划。

(Picture source: CDRF)

Guido Schmidt-Traub is Executive Director of the UN Sustainable Development Solutions Network, which operates under the auspices of the UN Secretary-General to support the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Climate Agreement. Board member of Water Aid and the Friends Europe of the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria and Associate Adjunct Professor at Sunway University

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(Malaysia). Before, managed the MDG Support Team at UNDP (2006-2008) and served as Policy Advisor and then as Associate Director of the UN Millennium Project in New York

Guido Schmidt-Traub

Partner, SYSTEMIQ LTD

Dr. Guido Schmidt-Traub is Executive Director of the UN Sustainable Development Solutions Network, which operates under the auspices of the UN Secretary-General to support the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Climate Agreement. Guido leads the SDSN's policy work, including on nature-based solutions. He is a Board member of Water Aid and the Friends Europe of the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria as well as Associate Adjunct Professor at Sunway University (Malaysia). Previously, Guido was CEO of Paris-based CDC Climat Asset Management, an investment company regulated by the French financial markets regulator; climate change advisor to the Africa Progress Panel secretariat; and Director and Partner at South Pole Carbon Asset Management in Zurich. He managed the MDG Support Team at UNDP (2006-2008) and served as Policy Advisor and then as Associate Director of the UN Millennium Project in New York, which was tasked with developing an action plan to achieve the Millennium Development Goals and advised countries around the world on their implementation. Earlier he was Partner at IndexIT Scandinavia, a private equity fund for early-stage technology companies, and consultant at McKinsey & Company in Germany. Guido holds a Ph.D. in Economics from Wageningen University & Research, an M.Phil. in Economics from Oxford University (Rhodes Scholar), and a Masters in physical chemistry from the Free University Berlin. He resides in Paris with his family.

(Picture source: World Economic Forum)

2.3 Peking University China Center for Public Finance: member of Advisory Committee

1. What is Peking University China Center for Public Finance?

It is dedicated to research on taxation, government public goods provision and infrastructure construction, income redistribution, pension and medical security, fiscal deficit and government debt, local finance, and central-local fiscal relations and others. The center is an important base for China's fiscal research, a high-level platform for academic cooperation and exchanges in the field of finance between China and foreign countries, and a think tank that provides fiscal and tax policy advice to the central and local governments. The center aims to promote the improvement of China's public finance research level, promote the continuous deepening of China's fiscal reform.

Since its establishment, the China Public Finance Research Center of Peking University has organized various types of international academic seminars, and held China Public Finance Forums, and held discussions with the United States, Britain, Germany, France, Japan, South Korea, Singapore, Australia, Canada, Brazil and other countries. Scholars established close academic exchanges, conducted in-depth local investigations and research, and successfully completed a number of scientific research projects of the Ministry of Finance, SASAC, Ministry of Industry and Information, World Bank, United Nations and local governments, and published collections of academic papers, working papers, and financial briefings.

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CPF 北京大学中国公共财政研究中心
Peking University China Center For Public Finance

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杰弗里·萨克斯 (Jeffrey Sachs)

教授综述

现任:
哥伦比亚大学地球研究所的教授及所长, 同时为联合国秘书长潘基文的特别顾问

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北京大学中国公共财政研究中心
Peking University China Center For Public Finance

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中心概况 > 中心概况

中心概况

中心概况

发布日期: 来源:

北京大学中国公共财政研究中心是2006年成立的学术研究机构。中心致力于税收、政府公共品提供和基础设施建设、收入再分配、养老和医疗保障、财政赤字和政府债务、地方财政、以及中央地方财政关系等理论和政策方面的研究。中心是中国财政研究的重要基地，是中外财政领域学术合作和交流的高级平台，是为中央和地方政府提供财税政策咨询的智库。中心旨在促进中国公共财政研究水平提高，促进中国财政改革不断深化，促进中国经济持续发展和民生不断改善。

自成立以来，北京大学中国公共财政研究中心组织了各种类型的国际学术研讨会，召开中国公共财政论坛，与美国、英国、德国、法国、日本、韩国、新加坡、澳大利亚、加拿大、巴西等国学者建立密切学术交往，深入地方调查研究，出色完成了国家财政部、国资委、工业与信息化部、世界银行、联合国以及地方政府的多项科研项目，出版学术论文集、工作论文、以及财政简报，为中国财政改革做出了积极贡献。

(Picture source: CCPF)

2. Who else are on the payroll?

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Peking University China Center For Public Finance

首页 | 中心概况 | **组织结构** | 研究员团队 | 学术活动 | 学术成果

首页 > 组织结构 > 顾问委员会

组织结构

- 顾问委员会
- 理事会
- 学术委员会
- 执行委员会

厉以宁
主席，北京大学光华管理学院经济学教授
研究领域:

詹姆斯·莫里斯 (James A. Mirrlees)
主席，1996年诺贝尔经济学奖得主 英国剑桥大学教授
研究领域:

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安兰·阿沃班克 (Alan Auerbach)

 教授综述

现任:

加州大学 (伯克利分校) 公共财政与税收研究中心主任, 教授

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杰弗里·萨克斯 (Jeffrey Sachs)

哥伦比亚大学地球研究所的教授及所长，同时为联合国秘书长潘基文的特别顾问

研究领域：

劳伦斯·考特里克夫 (Laurence Kotlikoff)

波士顿大学经济学教授，经济安全计划主席

研究领域：

路易斯·波尔 (Louis Pol)

内布拉斯加州奥马哈大学商业与管理学院教授

研究领域：

林毅夫

第十三届全国政协常委、经济委员会副主任，北京大学新结构经济学研究院、南南合作发展院院长、国家发展研究院名誉院长

研究领域：

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黄朝翰

前新加坡国立大学东亚研究所学术所长

研究领域：

胡永泰 (Wing Thye Woo)

美国加州大学戴维斯分校经济系教授

研究领域：

谢旭人

前社保基金会理事长、党组成员，前财政部部长

研究领域：

易纲

北京大学经济学院顾问委员会委员，中国人民银行行长、党委副书记

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詹姆斯·莫里斯 (James A. Mirrlees)

 教授综述

现任:
主席, 1996年诺贝尔经济学奖得主 英国剑桥大学教授

(Picture source: CCPF)

2.4 Tsinghua University's Global Institute for Sustainable Development: Chairman of the International Academic Committee

Tsinghua University Global Institute for Sustainable Development was established in 2017 to carry out interdisciplinary, cross-disciplinary, interdisciplinary, interdisciplinary professional research institutions. The establishment of the Institute was to respond to the United Nations 2030 sustainable development agenda, strengthen scientific research in the field of sustainable development goals, personnel training and international cooperation and exchange, boosting China's sustainable development process and contributing Chinese wisdom and experience to global sustainable development when "Global Cooperation Summit Forum" was held in Beijing at Tsinghua University. In the ceremony

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Jeffrey Sachs read the congratulatory letter from the United Nations Secretary General Guterrez.

2020-04-08 [大 中 小]

北京时间3月30日晚，联合国可持续发展解决方案网络（UNSDSN）就“新冠肺炎的流行病学与经济学”热点议题召开线上国际研讨会，旨在探讨新冠肺炎（COVID-19）对公共卫生及可持续发展目标（SDGs）造成的影响及其科学的应对措施。国际货币基金组织战略、政策和审查部主任马丁·穆赫雷森（Martin Mühleisen），耶鲁大学公共卫生学院传染性疾病预防与分析中心主任艾莉森·加尔瓦尼（Alison P. Galvani），韩国车医科大学医学院教授、健康产业学院院长Jun Byung-yool，清华大学全球可持续发展研究院（清华SDG研究院）国际学术委员会主席、联合国可持续发展解决方案网络主任、哥伦比亚大学经济学教授杰弗里·萨克斯（Jeffrey Sachs），清华大学公共管理学院副教授、清华SDG研究院骨干研究员高宇宁受邀参与本次网络会议，与来自全球各国的数十位业界专家从“疫情现状、防控措施、经济影响与对策、疫苗与治疗手段”四个维度对这场席卷全球的疫情展开了全面剖析。

The image shows a video conference interface. At the top, a small video window displays Jeffrey Sachs speaking. Below it is a large presentation slide with the following text:

Some Economics of Fighting Covid-19

Jeffrey D. Sachs
March 30, 2020

SDSN Webinar on:
The Epidemiology and Economics of Covid-19

At the bottom of the slide, there is a small SDSN logo and some navigation icons.

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(Picture Source: sppm)

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(Picture source: sdgpyramid)

2.5 Bund Finance Summit: Lecturer

At the 2nd Bund Finance Summit held by the China Financial Forty Forum (CF40) by organizing various committee members on 24 October 2020, Jeffrey Sachs, delivered a keynote speech *Environmentally sustainable and socially sustainable methods to promote the recovery of the global economy are an important issue facing countries all over the world.* The chairman of the summit organizing committee is Yuan Chen, vice chairman of the 12th National Committee of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference and chairman of the Standing Council of the China Financial Forty Forum, and the executive chairman is Guangshao Tu, executive director of the China Financial Forty Forum and chairman of the Shanghai New Finance Research Institute.

He made speech to downplay dollars against other currencies and suggest circumventing dollar settlement in the first summit held on 27 October 2019 when Yuan Chen and Guangshao Tu were also chairman and executive chairman .

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— 2020 —
10/27
21:06

中国金融四十
人论坛
企鵝号

— 分享 —

— 评论 —

10月24日，在由**中国金融四十人论坛（CF40）**联合各组委会成员机构召开的**第二届外滩金融峰会**上，美国哥伦比亚大学校级教授、联合国秘书长前特别顾问**Jeffrey SACHS**发表主题演讲表示，如何以环境可持续和社会可持续的方式来推进全球经济复苏进程，是当前全球各国面临的一个重要问题。

为保障可持续发展，外滩金融峰会设立组委会，组委会是峰会的最高决策机构。峰会组委会主席由十二届全国政协副主席、中国金融四十人论坛常务理事**陈元**担任，执行主席由中国金融四十人论坛常务理事、上海新金融研究院理事长**屠光绍**担任。

(Picture source: QQ)

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外灘金融峰会 BUND SUMMIT

外灘金融峰会

BUND SUMMIT

2019年10月27-29日

— 中国·上海外滩 —

直击现场 会议议程 媒体报道

2019年10月27日 2019年10月28日

全体大会 I: 开放与融通——全球视野下的新金融、新经济

主持人: 王海明 中国金融四十人论坛秘书长、上海新金融研究院执行院长

8:30

🕒 8:30-9:00

📅 嘉宾签到

9:00

🕒 9:00-9:20

📅 致欢迎辞

吴清 上海市人民政府副市长

屠光绍 外滩金融峰会组委会执行主席、中国金融四十人论坛常务理事、上海新金融研究院理事长

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9:20

🕒 9:20-12:15

📅 主题演讲

陈元 外滩金融峰会组委会主席、中国金融四十人论坛常务理事兼主席、十二届全国政协副主席

金墉 全球基础设施合伙公司副董事长兼合伙人、世界银行第12任行长

肖钢 中国金融四十人论坛资深研究员

缪建民 CF40常务理事、中国人民保险集团董事长

彭纯 中国投资有限责任公司董事长

陆磊 CF40成员、国家外汇管理局副局长

黄益平 CF40学术委员会主席、北京大学数字金融研究中心主任

Sir Dave RAMSDEN 英格兰银行副行长

Lord Adair TURNER 新经济思维研究院高级研究员、英国金融服务管理局原主席

Jeffrey SACHS 美国哥伦比亚大学教授、联合国秘书长前特别顾问

(Picture source: finance.china)

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【10月27日，首届外滩金融峰会在上海开幕。在当天上午的全体大会“开放与融通——全球视野下的新金融、新经济”上，美国哥伦比亚大学教授、联合国前高级顾问杰弗里·萨克斯（Jeffery Sachs）发表主旨演讲，他认为，上海是最领先的金融中心，同时以美元为主导的体制过渡到人民币、欧元、美元多种货币的体制会很快到来。但这不是人民币取代美元，而是成为一个关键性的国际货币，与美元“平起平坐”，这跟上世纪30年代是不一样的，未来是多种货币并立的一个时代。

【以下为杰弗里·萨克斯演讲全文。】

(Picture source: guanacha)

2.6 Hanwang Forum

On 9 May 2012, the world's first Hanwang Forum was grandly held in Diaoyutai State Guesthouse, Beijing. Xiulian Gu(Vice Chairman of the Standing Committee of the 10th National People's Congress), Meng Li(Vice Chairman of the 10th National Committee of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference), Wenfan Zhang(Former Vice Minister of the PRC Ministry of Civil Affairs), Aubarsada(Nigerian Ambassador to China and Permanent Representative of Nigeria to the United

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Nations), Jeffrey Sachs and others attended the forum.

全球第一届汉旺论坛在北京钓鱼台国宾馆隆重举行

首届汉旺论坛暨2012全球防灾、救灾与可持续发展国际论坛由德阳市人民政府、北京国际交流协会可持续发展专业委员会联合中国公共关系协会、中国医学救援协会、中国家庭服务业协会、中国华夏文化遗产基金会、中国残联华夏文化集团、中国建筑节能减排产业联盟等国内相关机构与社会团体共同举办。还特邀了联合国开发计划署、联合国工业发展组织中国代表处、国际应急救援学会等国际机构共同举办。

第十届全国人大常委会副委员长顾秀莲，第十届全国政协副主席李蒙，中国公共关系协会会长苏秋成，民政部前副部长张文范，德阳市委副书记、市长陈新有，北京国际交流协会可持续发展专业委员会会长魏志远出席，气候繁荣战略协会副主席Lawrence Bloom，尼日利亚驻中国大使暨尼日利亚驻联合国永久代表Aubarsada，联合国秘书长高级顾问Jeffrey Sachs及多个国家的各界领

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(Picture source: tance)

5月9日，首届汉旺论坛在北京举行，论坛围绕全球防灾减灾和可持续发展为主题展开交流和对话。图为联合国秘书长高级顾问Jeffrey Sachs在主席台就坐。（中国网和中国发展门户网记者胡迪、刘字明、玄萱摄影并报道）

(Picture source: chinagate)

2.7 "Belt and Road Initiative" Green Development International Alliance

On 10 September 2020, the "Belt and Road" Green Development International Alliance held a webinar on alliance flagship report "The Belt and Road Initiative Green Development Report" and BRIGC Thematic Partnerships Working Meeting. Solheim, Chairman of the Alliance Advisory Committee, Senior Advisor of the World Resources Institute, Jeffrey Sachs, and Yonghong Li, Deputy Director of the Foreign Cooperation and Exchange Center of the Ministry of Ecology and Environment attended Meeting and delivered a speech. More than 80 people including Denis Nkala, Asia-Pacific Regional Coordinator of the United Nations Office for South-South Cooperation, Jianyu Zhang, Vice President of the U.S. Environmental Protection Association, John Mimikakis, and Xufeng Zhu, Associate Dean of the School of Public Administration, Tsinghua University Delegates attended the meeting online.

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中华人民共和国生态环境部
Ministry of Ecology and Environment of the People's Republic of China

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业务工作

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“一带一路”绿色发展国际联盟在线召开《“一带一路”绿色发展报告》与联盟专题伙伴关系工作协调会

2020-09-16

字号: [大] [中] [小] [打印]

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2020年9月10日，“一带一路”绿色发展国际联盟（简称联盟）在线召开联盟旗舰报告《“一带一路”绿色发展报告》（简称旗舰报告）与专题伙伴关系工作协调会。联盟咨询委员会主任委员、世界资源研究所高级顾问索尔海姆，联合国可持续发展解决方案网络（SDSN）主任杰弗里·萨克斯（Jeffrey Sachs），生态环境部对外合作与交流中心副主任李永红出席会议。

2020年9月10日，“一带一路”绿色发展国际联盟（简称联盟）在线召开联盟旗舰报告《“一带一路”绿色发展报告》（简称旗舰报告）与专题伙伴关系工作协调会。联盟咨询委员会主任委员、世界资源研究所高级顾问索尔海姆，联合国可持续发展解决方案网络（SDSN）主任杰弗里·萨克斯（Jeffrey Sachs），生态环境部对外合作与交流中心副主任李永红出席会议并致辞。联合国南南合作办公室亚太区域协调员丹尼斯·恩卡拉（Denis Nkala）、美国环保协会副总裁张建宇、约翰·米米卡克斯（John Mimikakis）、清华大学公共管理学院副院长朱旭峰等80余名代表在线参加会议。

索尔海姆在致辞中表示，“一带一路”是这个时代最重要的倡议之一，希望通过旗舰报告捕捉更多绿色发展的经验并向世界推广。杰弗里·萨克斯表示，绿色“一带一路”能够在环境和社会层面帮助中国发挥巨大的领导力，从而推动全球清洁、绿色、数字技术的发展。李永红在致辞中指出，国际社会高度关注和期待“一带一路”在引领全球绿色复苏中发挥重要作用，联盟将继续发挥合作伙伴优势和平台作用，为推动“一带一路”绿色发展发挥更加积极的作用。

联盟秘书处及清华大学可持续发展研究院汇报了联盟及旗舰报告的最新工作进展。联盟生物多样性、气候变化、海洋治理、绿色金融、绿色技术创新、南南合作、可持续交通、绿色城市、环境法律标准等专题伙伴关系代表围绕报告研究大纲、重点领域、绿色案例等方面的问题进行了讨论，并对如何融入专题伙伴关系相关成果提出了具体意见和建议。

(Picture source: Gov.cn)

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2.8 Defend Hong Kong National Security Law

In an exclusive interview with Ta Kung Pao on 20 July 2021, Sachs said that the US unilateral sanctions were wrong and said that the outside world had potential misunderstandings about the Hong Kong National Security Law. He believed that the situation in Hong Kong can and should be normalized, and that it can also protect Hong Kong's economy and way of life.

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图：萨克斯接受《大公报》独家书面访问。

7月16日，美国政府发布所谓“香港商业警告”，肆意抹黑香港营商环境，并对七名中方官员作出所谓“制裁”。《大公报》昨独家书面专访美国知名经济学家、前联合国秘书长特别顾问杰弗里·大卫·萨克斯 (Jeffrey David Sachs)，他表示，美国应尊重中国的主权和领土完整，所谓“制裁”是错误的做法，也于事无补，对话才是正道。

萨克斯表示看好香港，看好香港前景，香港至今仍是全球金融、旅游和贸易中心，这符合包括美国和中国在内全世界的利益。

现任美国哥伦比亚大学经济学教授的萨克斯，曾在2001至2018年连续担任三任联合国秘书长的特别顾问，目前是联合国可持续发展解决方案网络负责人，《纽约时报》曾形容他是“全球最重要的经济学家”。

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美国著名经济学家杰弗瑞·萨克斯接受BBC采访谈气候变化，但主持人却以中国“侵犯人权”为前提来提问

为啥不谈谈美国侵犯人权的行爲呢？

▲ 薩克斯接受BBC訪問時，狠批該機構記者雙標，惡意針對中國，但避談美國侵犯人權的問題。

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批拜登政府对华政策粗暴

萨克斯在20日接受《大公报》专访时称，美国单边制裁是错误的，实际上美方的所谓“指控”和单边制裁也于事无补。他表示，外界对香港国安法有潜在误解，他相信香港的局势能够而且应该正常化，并可兼顾到保护香港的经济和生活方式；同时要尊重中国主权和领土完整；拜登政府从上台第一天起就对中国粗鲁不堪，这在外交政策上是不可接受的，也是一种极其危险的做法。

萨克斯认为，只有对话才是解决问题的方式，中美政府需进行高层、持续和系统的对话。

不久前国际货币基金组织发表报告，再次肯定香港国际金融中心地位。而香港美国商会也发表声明，强调香港仍是重要国际商业中心。对此，萨克斯表示“看好香港前景，香港是世界最大的贸易中心、金融中心以及港口和旅游城市，未来仍是全球主要的商业、金融、旅游和贸易中心，这符合包括美国和中国在内全世界的利益。”

除了涉港问题，美国也借人权、涉疆等问题频频干涉中国内政。萨克斯表示，拜登自上台执政就对中国指手画脚，进行粗暴干涉，这是不能接受的做法，不仅会导致局势紧张不断升级，甚至会推向潜在的军备竞赛，这是很危险的。他认为，美国新政府本应重新开始，尤其是在美国现代史上最糟糕的总统特朗普的不负责任的行为之后。他希望拜登政府能改变前任的做法，重新站在对华尊重的立场，“我们需要世界上最强大的两个国家之间进行高层对话。”

(Picture source: takungpao)

2.9 Downplay Xinjiang Genocide

On 20 April 2021 Jeffrey Sachs thought there was no genocide in Xinjiang without observing mounting evidences and biasedly and baselessly adopted the saying of CCP that the essence of Xinjiang-related issues was anti-violence, de-radicalization, and anti-separatism.

3 [What Chinese dissidents has suffered because of UNHCR's malpractice](#)

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Considering Jeffrey Sachs a senior UN officer in essence favouring CCP and interacting with CCP frequently and materially, especially in human rights issues, both in Xinjiang Genocide and crime against humanity both in Xinjiang and Hong Kong, it's unreasonable to expect that those Chinese dissidents seeking political asylum wouldn't be harmed by The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). During the process of seeking political asylum, Chinese dissidents undoubtedly provided identity documents such as passport and ID card, filled forms and were taken photos. If the information supplied by them were supplied to CCP due to coordination by Jeffrey Sachs, it would place asylum seekers in extreme danger resulting in refugee application being rejected, being expatriated to PRC and being arrested.

In 2020 it was reported by [Wion](#) that UN Human Rights office secretly provided the Chinese government names of activists critical of the Communist Party of China and their atrocities.

In 2020 it was reported by [I24News](#) that both Reilly and UN Watch asserted that China uses the information that the UN provides them, to harass human rights activists and their families - often accusing them of terrorism and worse. Reilly, a human rights lawyer working for the United Nations (UN) in Geneva, has accused the body's Human Rights Council of actively [passing names of Uighur dissidents to CCP](#) and 'her boss' was the one passing on names to CCP. Reilly has been frozen out of the UN - where she still works - and it transpires that nobody can take the matter to a court because the United Nations has diplomatic immunity.

This kind of news had been reported in [2019](#) and [2021](#).

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4 Jeffrey Sachs lacks integrity and objectivity.

Jeffrey Sachs argued for Kristalina Georgieva at Financial Times by ignoring specific [wrongdoings of Kristalina Georgieva](#). Jeffrey Sachs didn't tell FT readers his interest in China.

Jeffrey Sachs SEPTEMBER 27 2021

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The writer is director of the Center for Sustainable Development at Columbia University

The heated attack against IMF managing director **Kristalina Georgieva** is not really about the alleged sanctity of World Bank data or about the quality of her management. It is about the role of China in a Washington-based multilateral institution. Many in the US Congress want Georgieva out because she is not a sworn enemy of Beijing.

According to three Republican congressmen in their [letter to Treasury secretary Janet Yellen](#), the allegations against Georgieva “illustrate how the

(Picture source: FT)